

IoT and Deep Learning on Sensor Data

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Abstract— Internet of things (IoT) combined with machine learning algorithms has several applications in various fields. Extensive research and projects are available in Intrusion detection systems (IDS). This paper focuses on collecting data from various sensors and storing them efficiently in various database systems and applying machine learning algorithms to extract useful information from raw sensor data. We propose a 3-tier system that consists of sensor nodes, a sensor database, combined with machine learning algorithm for predicting the activity performed by the human at that point in time. The dataset used to train the Machine learning algorithm has been collected and stored in a NoSQL database which is non-relational and easily scalable. This work compares the reliability and accuracy of the existing algorithms in the field of IoT in sensor data.

Keywords— Internet of Things (IoT); Machine learning; NoSQL; sensors from smartphone; sensors from smartwatch

I. INTRODUCTION

Internet of things (IoT) combined with machine learning algorithms has several applications in various fields. The number of sensors are rapidly increasing leading to collection of lot of sensor data. Enormous amounts of sensor data decrease the functionality of standard SQL database; hence a NoSQL database is preferred to store the data [1]. This data can be beneficial if analysed using the right machine learning algorithms.

We have applied different machine learning algorithms on automatically gathered sensor dataset with manual data from a different control to predict the current activity performed. The dataset used to train the machine learning algorithm contains data from 60 users, each identified with a universally unique identifier (UUID) [2]. The data is collected from sensors in the user's smartwatch and smartphone at a regular interval of 1 minute. All the data collected have context labels self-reported by the user. We manually collected data for all the fields of required sensor data from our personal smart appliances and aligned them with the available dataset [3-6] to train our machine learning algorithm which can then predict the type of activity being performed.

We have used the sensor data from smartphone and smartwatches to predict the activity [7]. Besides, smartphone and smartwatches similar sensor data can also be used to perform these machine learning algorithms and technique to get the desired result.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2: Literature survey, Section 3: Proposed System, Section 4 Proposed algorithms, while Section 5 interpretation and evaluation of the result, Section 6: we draw the conclusion and provide direction for future work.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

There has not been any exact implementation of the 3-tier system, but a similar proposed system can be found in this work [8]. They have implemented a vertical system with no database for the sensor data, while manually providing all the input data for the machine learning algorithm. The concepts of machine learning are widely used, the classification algorithm (decision tree) and linear regression are implemented in numerous projects. For better understanding of the machine learning algorithm in reference [9] provides an in-depth understanding of the algorithms. The algorithm from this paper has played a significant role in our paper.

NoSQL databases are preferred over SQL database for storing sensor data. The performance and scalability of the NoSQL databases are better than SQL database [10].

Machine learning algorithm has been applied on irrigation sensors, to improve plant growth conditions. This paper contains detailed explanations of the modules [11]. The result of this paper shows that non-parametric models provide a more accurate irrigation prediction than linear regression model. GBRT and BTC models had respective accuracy of 93% and 95%, however they provided more complex models spanning over 50 decision trees. The linear regression algorithm took far more transformations to capture non-linear relationship between the sensors. All the algorithms have been discussed in recent researches [12].

The next step in our work is to take the collected sensor data and store it in the cloud. Providing machine learning services on the cloud. Quite similar implementation is available but not with machine learning. This compares different cloud services providing a clear ranking to choose from the cloud service [13]. This can be further expanded to ratings, for more refer [14].

Problem Statement:

The growth in number of sensors used is increasing rapidly, hence the data produced is multiplying with time. It has become impossible to analysis bulk amounts of sensor data manually. In the future we need to make fast and intelligent decision based on sensor data. This is need in various field (e.g., medicine, self-driving car). The way to achieve this is applying machine learning algorithm on the sensor data. We have proposed a 3-tier system to gather, store and apply machine learning algorithm on the sensor data.

III. PROPOSED 3-TIER SYSTEM

The components of the proposed 3-tier System (Fig.1) are: Sensor nodes, a database to store the sensor data, Human component to provide the input data, ML toolkit and the final prediction result format. The sensor data has been previously gathered by [15], and stored in mongo DB. The input data is of very similar type to the previously collected data with identically sensor fields.

Fig. 1. The 3 tier System

Sensors

The sensors are from smartphone and smartwatch which were supplied to the users. The users were undergraduate and graduate students of the university.

statistics over the 60 users:

Only the records with clear lading by the user was preserved in the database and later used with the machine learning algorithm for a more accurate result.

Data gathering

The sensors used were of several types motion-reactive sensors, location, audio, navigation compass that were collected once a minute

The original label which has been reported by the users have been cleaned and classified into 51 labels [16].

The labels are of two types:

Major activity:

Labels describing movement of the user. This category is of the 5 possible values: sleeping, travelling, walking, running, cycling.

Minor activity:

Minor activity label gives more specific details of the activity: playing football, gym, with friends, movie, school.

A single record of data can be associated with multiple labels.

IV. PROPOSED ALGORITHMS

Regression:

For applying the linear regression, the labels should have a numeric value. Motion sensor had values (1 to 0) corresponding to extremely fast and stationary. Heart rate had numeric value which was the original heart rate divided by 90.

Linear regression algorithm the output is a continuous line and with a constant slope. It can predict the values with a particular ranger instead of classifying them into different label types [17].

There are two types of regression algorithm:

Simple regression:

Simple linear regression function is of normal slop-intercept format.

$$Y = mX + b$$

In this equation m and b are the variables of the algorithm or the parameters to classify the datasets. Simple regression can be used in the case of 2 variables. In this paper there are 3 parameters: motion sensor, Heart rate, Temperature.

Hence Multivariable regression is used:

Multivariable regression equations are more complex, the function value being dependent on more than 2 variables.

$$F(X,Y,Z) = W1 X + W2 Y + W3 Y$$

Here X,Y,Z are the parameters: : motion sensor, Heart rate, Temperature.

Regression Algorithm:

Label = W1* motionsensor + W2 * heartrate + W3 * temperature

Walking < 0.313

Cycling < 0.456

0.194 < Travelling && Travelling > 0.765

W(1,2,3) are the function defining sensor value to the algorithm.

Classification

Decision tree builds a classification model in form of a tree structure. Dataset is broken down into smaller subsets, while the height of the tree is developed. The final result, leaf nodes are the decision nodes which classifies the label type [18].

Fig. 2 displays the decision tree for the datasets. Both decision trees have motion sensor measurement in their root node, which can easily identify all the records where the users are stationary and moving. The simple dataset contains 3 attributes used for labelling the record: motion sensor, heart rate, temperature.

V. INTERPRETATION AND EVALUATION OF THE RESULT

To compare the prediction result of both the algorithm, we performed the experiment on two different datasets: Normal dataset where it contains only the sensor attributes and label types, the second dataset contains additional data which has been introduced by the human component.

Classification algorithm: decision tree and linear regression algorithm have been applied on these datasets. A completed working and implementation of these algorithm is available on [19].

From the table it can be observed how the algorithms have performed on both the dataset (simple and augmented).

J48 in the table indicates the decision tree algorithm. MAE is the mean absolute error while RMSCE indicates the root mean squared error. These values show the error in prediction.

Both the algorithms have had better result with the augmented dataset [20], which shows that combining the dataset with additional manually gathered data can improve the prediction. It is clear the decision tree (j48) algorithm outperforms linear regression on both the dataset.

Both the algorithms have benefits of their own, choosing the right one for your application depends on what your needs are, decision tree gives better result than linear regression but is very complex and requires high computing power for large dataset. Linear regression is much less complex when

Fig. 2. Decision Tree

compared with decision tree, but the accuracy is less. The accuracy can be increased with larger datasets. When comparing both the algorithms, we found model generated by decision tree is more diversified and highly accurate

The results of this experiment provide us encouragement to expand our 3-tier system in the future. The system can be improved by increasing the sensor quality and quantity. Once the datasets are enormous, next step is to move the database to the cloud and apply the machine learning on the data stored in the cloud. Eventually improving from 3-tier to 4-tier System.

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Fig. 3. Accuracy Graph

The graph (Fig. 3) is plotted against accuracy of both the algorithm vs the size of the dataset. From the graph it is noticeably clear that the decision tree algorithm provides much better prediction result than the linear regression model. The graph when plotted for the augmented dataset had very similar curve. The difference between both models diminishes as the size of the dataset keeps growing, hence for large volumes of dataset we recommend linear regression, which provides reasonably good performance with less complexity.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper proposed a 3-tier System for predicting the type of activity performed by the user at that point in time based on the data from the smartphone and smartwatch sensors. We labelled the sensors data with additional information to create an augmented dataset. We concluded that the type of activity can be predicted to an extent using the sensors from smartphone and smartwatch. The prediction result for both the algorithm is better when the additional information was added. The accuracy rate of the algorithm is better when we filtered the sensor data to remove abnormal records.

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